

THE EFFECT OF USING DISCOURSE ANALYSIS METHOD ON IMPROVING COGNITIVE AND AFFECTIVE SKILLS IN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE TEACHINGⁱ

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to identify the effect of using discourse analysis method on the skills of reading comprehension, textual analysis, creating discourse and use of language. In this study, the authentic test model with pre-test and post-test control group was used in order to determine the difference of academic achievement between experimental group, with which discourse analysis method in literature teaching was used and of control group, where traditional teaching methods used. Moreover, students' opinions and thoughts on the use of discourse analysis method in literature teaching were also gathered. In the analysis of quantitative data, arithmetic mean, standard deviation, frequency, t-test for dependent samples and t-test for independent samples were used. Students' opinions and thoughts on the use of discourse analysis method in language and literature teaching were gathered through video-recording and transcribed to analyze through descriptive and content analysis approaches. The study group of the research consists of 11th grade students of Bilkent Erzurum Laboratory School in 2014-2015 Academic year, 20 (11/A) students of experimental group and 24 (11/B) students of control group. The data of the study were gathered through achievement tests, video-recording, student identification and classroom observation; developed by the researcher in accordance with quantitative and qualitative research techniques. Within this scope, an "achievement test" in order to evaluate students' readiness level; a "student identification form" to get information about students and interview to identify students' opinions on the use of discourse analysis method in literature teaching were conducted. As a result of this study, it can be affirmed that in experimental group, who used discourse analysis method, skills of reading comprehension, textual analysis and use of language were improved in addition to their

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academic success. When the process of applying discourse analysis method and its findings were examined, it can be concluded that this method helps students to develop their skills of reading comprehension, textual analysis, use of language, critical thinking, evaluative thinking, analysis and synthesis and provides environments in which meaningful and permanent learning can be achieved, can be transferred to and used in other areas. Additionally, it is very effective on students, increases students' active participation in lessons by making lessons more enjoyable, supports personal development of students by contributing to their social and communication skills. Thus, cognitive and affective developments of students were developed, which provides a holistic approach to educational practices.

Keywords: language and literature teaching, reading comprehension, textual analysis, discourse analysis method, language awareness

1. Introduction

In language and literature education; as long as reading process is performed and achieved effectively, in other words, when the 'understanding' is achieved, the objectives of these lessons can be reached. It can be said that each stage of education has reached its goal, if reading activity, which constitutes the backbone of all stages of education, results in comprehension. Therefore, comprehension acts like a measurement and assessment tool as to whether the reading activity has really taken place. This will be possible through a reading and analysing method to be used as teaching method, which draws attention to and fully comprehension of what students have read or see.

The results of the researches, observations, national and international examinations show skills of reading comprehension and interests of high school students towards language and literature lessons are not at desired levels. It is seen that students do not fully understand the texts they read because of lack of reading, understanding and textual analysis skills. The thought that the problem of understanding can be solved through the use of appropriate methods and techniques in a qualified learning environment, by increasing interests of students and their participation in lessons constitutes the main problem of this study. The use of such a method in literary lessons will help learners understand the texts as whole with all of its interrelated constituents by analysing and critically approaching it through thinking processes.

It is also known by observations, reading and analysing texts by traditional methods, realized in the form of paraphrase or repetition of the content (plot, theme etc.) in the text, are performed at the very superficial level compared to above mentioned acquisitions. In sum, a method that is thought to be a necessary condition for the understanding of texts, and which allows the whole to be fully and completely understood without neglecting any elements constituting it not only in surface but also in deep structure of the text, is necessary condition for understanding the texts because

the text is a production of language; and each text creates its own language. A method is needed to decipher these codes of language.

In order to achieve aimed targets and outcomes in language and literature lessons, which mainly focus on skills development, learners are to comprehend texts as they should be able to actively participate in the process of textual analysis, they should improve and actively use their higher order thinking skills as analysis, synthesis and evaluation by learning and applying textual analysis methods thoroughly. Moreover, it is only possible to reach those goals by considering the text with its all aspects and taking all of its parts as a whole without degrading it to one of its parts (as content, form, context, author or reader) and by adopting such a method that gives way that kind of comprehension and analysis process.

To use such an analysis method in literature lessons will help students analyze texts properly, adopt critical approach and thinking, get the meaning in texts as a whole unit with all of its parts taken into account, and also comprehend the relationship between the individual parts of a text that serve certain aims to create meaning. Helping students gain fundamental skills is regarded as the main aim of language and literature programs. These skills can be classified as reading, listening, speaking, writing and linguistic knowledge, and that these skills are beyond the boundaries of language and literature courses since they are effective, important and valuable skills in all areas of life. Given the importance of reading skill, by which understanding is meant, searching for and findings about the techniques, assessment tools, and more efficient and inclusive methods to be developed and used, will always be important and these studies will always provide significant contributions to the science of education.

Therefore, in this study, to determine the effect of the method on language and literature lessons, the answers for the questions as; whether the discourse analysis method creates difference in the areas and skills mentioned, between the group where the method used and the one where it was not used and whether any kind of changes occurred in the opinions and interests of the students, before and after the method in question integrated to language and literature lessons, will be tried to get. Therefore, it is aimed to compare the discourse analysis method with the regular instruction by researching the effect of discourse analysis method on some skills as comprehension, analysis, use of language and making discourse and also on their interest and participation in the lessons under discussion.

1.1 Discourse Analysis

Discourse is defined as a concept used to describe syntactic linguistic order consisting of certain principles, rules, terminology and conventions (Tonkiss, 2006: 370).

Discourse occurs when the language is used functionally, in a written and verbal setting, in a purposeful, useful and functional way. Discourse includes not only the content of a message but also the way in which it is expressed, which and how elements are chosen and brought together for a specific reason, in what context, for which aim and target group, in which direction it is intended to effect audience, and what kind of atmosphere is created by benefiting from which opportunities of language. Each

reading is at the same time is a writing activity and so, there is always something to say on text, as long as writing process exists; in other words, writing requires reading afterwards (Günay, 2007; Günay, 2013; Agger, 1992).

The text is a meaningful unit. A text 'understanding' or 'meaning' can be defined as reaching the text and its declaration by analysing or deconstructing the composition and its components that brought together by taking their semantic and contextual values into consideration.

The concept of discourse analysis was first used by the conceptual linguist Zellig Harris to investigate the principle that linked sentences to each other in a text. While searching for rules for why a sentence followed by another, Harris identified two possible directions for the discourse analysis. One of them is the connection of language and culture, and the other is the continuous descriptive linguistics beyond the limits of a single sentence (Harris, 1952: 474-485). Discourse analysis then came to the foreground of the research areas at the end of the 1970's, and the reflections of the method were first on philosophical arguments, hermeneutics and on the constructive role of language on social reality (Sinclair and Coulthard 1975, Van Dijk 1985, Potter and Wetherell 1987, Fairclough 1995, 1996, Titscher et al. 2000).

Discourse analysis is a comprehensive research method that deals with meaning output derived from verbal and written texts. Discourse refers to the processes of language practice that turns into action through meta-act, ideology, knowledge, conversation, narration, expression, negotiation, power and power shifts from one to another (Sözen, 1999: 74).

Among the basic assumptions of discourse analysis are; that language is an instrument in action and function, people use it linguistically for certain purposes, and this active fiction or construction process is reflected in the diversity of language. Language learning, even if it is a native language learning, is more than knowing grammar rules, and requires learning it in use. Moreover, language is expressed in discourse; the discourse is shaped in context and the context occurs in the text. In written discourse, literary texts present different discourses and contexts in different text types. Texts are used at every level of native or second language teaching process. What is important at this point is the comprehension of texts; which depends on the different conditions that arise from the reader or from the text. In this respect, the analysis of discourse can be regarded as a guidance through dark streets descending into the essence and depth of the text. Studies of discourse analysis focus on language in use that extends beyond sentence boundaries. Thus, reaching the hidden essence that lies beneath the surface presents a way to go beyond the boundaries of the sentence in order to ensure that the reader speaks the same language with 'subject of discourse' or speaking subject, in other words, author.

However, neither in the field of educational sciences nor in the field of mother tongue and literature teaching, there is other study or practice in which the effect of using discourse analysis as a method of teaching was investigated. Additionally, a study where effect of discourse analysis on reading and comprehension could not be encountered. There is also lack of studies on comprehension skills in language and

literature courses in general and the existing ones are mostly related to elementary education. Moreover, the lack of any study that examine the effect of discourse analysis method on this skill, demonstrates that this study may make a significant contribution to literature in education. It is foreseen that this study and its results will develop inferences and suggestions on the programs of teacher training, its essence, content, outcomes and methods; so it is thought to be an important study in this respect. Therefore, in this study to analyze the method of discourse analysis in literature teaching in terms of some variables and to compare the effectiveness of this method in comparison with traditional methods.

1.2 Problem

The effect of discourse analysis method on the skills of textual analysis, reading comprehension, creating written discourse; and on students' interest and participation in the lesson, will be examined. In response to this basic problem, answers to the following questions will be sought.

1.3 Research Questions

1. Is there any meaningful difference between the treatment group and control group in terms of 'comprehension' skill according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?
2. Is there any meaningful difference between the treatment group and control group in terms of 'analysis' skill according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?
3. Is there any meaningful difference between the treatment group and control group in terms of 'making discourse' skill according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?
4. Is there any meaningful difference between the treatment group and control group in terms of 'use of language' skill according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?
5. What are the thoughts and opinions of participants on using discourse analysis method?

2. Literature Review

Teaching method is an important issue that determines the success of the process from the beginning. The scope of knowledge and skills that students need to acquire through learning environments are increasing day by day, especially when it comes to the lessons aiming at developing skills that go beyond walls of classrooms, such as language and literature courses, methods should be changed, developed and enriched accordingly, in a fast and appropriate way. Moreover, it is clear that direct transfer of information and pure memorizing approach will not help students help those skills; since reading, understanding, writing and self-expression are the areas that require effective participation. Therefore, learning can not be realized through traditional and

teacher centered methods by which students don't attend or can not participate in the lessons.

Accordingly, studies has begun to be conducted to search for techniques and methods where students are in the center of learning process and make their active participation possible, by which students can perform cognitive processes to construct knowledge and skills by themselves (Maden, 2010: 3).

The role of reading and understanding in academic and social achievement has been in the focus of educational researchers for many years. Reading is not only an educational process but an activity that helps the individual understand and comprehend any verbal or nonverbal material better at every stage of his life and is known to be a decisive factor in the success of the individual in his / her life skills and academic area (Gallik, 1999).

The fact that love and comprehension of reading affect positively the overall academic achievement has been revealed as a result of many researches (Yılmaz, 2012; Yıldız, 2013; Ünal and Köksal, 2007, Katrancı, 2015).

Reading activity, which we can also refer to as application of knowledge, is regarded as both the indicator and dynamism of development in developed countries. In addition to acquiring a large part of the knowledge acquired in daily life through reading, all the processes that enable person to become conscious of his/her individuality, and to form individual identity, to have the equipment to locate himself / herself in the context of society, to increase his/her level of knowledge and to achieve many successes like these in the academic and social life can be enabled through reading activity (Özdemir, 1993).

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Research Design

This was a mixed experimental study in which both qualitative and quantitative methods used and designed to determine the effects of using discourse analysis method on the 'comprehension, analysis, making discourse and language use' achievement of eleventh-grade students. The independent variable was the discourse analysis method and the dependent variable was the level of comprehension achievement in eleventh-grade students, and the control group variable was the regular instruction of the school district curriculum.

In the pretest - posttest control group model, there are two groups, experimental and control group, formed by neutral assignment. Measurements are conducted before and after the experiment in both groups. The presence of the pre-tests in the model helps to correct the results of post-test according to the similarity levels of the groups before the experiment (Büyüköztürk, 2001, Hovardaoğlu, 2000, Karasar, 2012). The symbolic appearance of the model is as follows:

Table 1: Pretest – Posttest Control Group Model

G1	R	M1.1	X	O1.2
G2	R	M2.1		O2.2

Explanations of the abbreviations used in the design as follow:

G1: Experimental Group

G2: Control Group

M: Measurement

X: Independent Variable Level (Discourse Analysis Method)

As it is seen in the experimental research design, the studies and practices prepared for participants of 11th grade students to improve comprehension and expression skills through discourse analysis method were applied only to the experimental group. A special care was taken to ensure that the control group was not affected by studies performed on the experimental group. The control group maintained routine practices in the program. In the control group, the course book and the teacher's guide prepared in the light of the achievements in the MEB secondary education program were used.

3.2. Participants

The target group of this experimental study consisted of 2 eleventh-grade classrooms, totaling 44 students, chosen through the use of the convenience and purposive sampling approach. One of the Grade 11 classes, 11-A consisting of 20 students, was randomly chosen as experimental group and received the textual analysis instruction through the incorporation of discourse analysis method in texts. The other Grade 11 class (11-B) made up the control group, did not receive experimental treatment.

The study was conducted in a foundation laboratory school located in Erzurum, northeast of Turkey. The socio-economic and academic level of the students who participated in this study was equal and identified through the forms applied to students to know them better. The grade level taught in this school ranged from kindergarten to 12th grade.

3.3. Instruments

In the study, in accordance with the qualitative and quantitative research techniques, data were collected through achievement tests, student identification and observation forms and video recording of the students' opinions on the effect of discourse analysis method. Therefore, a pretest was prepared and conducted to assess students' readiness level in the beginning of the process, student identification form applied to know them better, a video-recorded interview was conducted to get the thoughts and opinions of students, and to increase the reliability of the data. The researcher also observed students' performance throughout the process and reflected her observations on observation forms and reports.

In order to ensure the reliability of the study, 4 experts' opinions were consulted and the reliability of the research was determined by comparing the agreements and

disagreements of the experts. The reliability of the research was determined using the formula of Miles and Huberman (1994:64) (Reliability = agreements / agreements + disagreements). According to Miles and Huberman (1994), it is regarded as desirable level when the consensus rate between experts and researchers get close to 90 % or when exceeds that rate. Consensus (reliability) rate was found as 91% through the reliability study carried out for this study. For the reliability of the assessment tool, content validity was checked to determine to what extent each dimension serves for the aims of the study. 3 subject area experts' and 4 assessment and evaluation experts' opinions were consulted to estimate how much the instrument represents every single element. In line with the experts' opinions, test was applied to 20 students in the pretreatment process to define and handle the deficiencies of it. The reliability of test's pretreatment was checked by test-retest method and the correlation value of test's pretreatment was found as 0,81. The comprehensibility of the last version of the test was evaluated in accordance with the experts' opinions; and test was adapted appropriately.

3.4. Data Analysis

Qualitative and quantitative analysis techniques were used to analyze the data. Arithmetic mean, frequency, standard deviation, independent t-test were used to analyze quantitative data. Independent t-test was used to compare the pre and post tests of treatment and control groups.

Descriptive and content analysis approaches were used to analyze quantitative data. In descriptive analysis, direct quotations are frequently given place to reflect students' opinions conspicuously. In descriptive analysis, the aim is to interpret data by organizing and present them in content integrity. For this purpose, firstly, gathered data were described in a logical and clear way, codes were categorized, themes were defined and all of them were interpreted.

4. Results and Discussion

In this study, the effects of integrating discourse analysis method into language and literature lessons in terms of some skills were tried to be identified. Thus, the method was applied for 4 months on treatment group to get the answer; whether it would create any difference between groups in terms of reading comprehension, textual analysis, making discourse and use of language skills before and after the experiment. The findings for practices of discourse analysis method for educational process were analyzed. Lastly, opinions and thoughts of the treatment groups on the use of the method were gathered through video recording and forms.

As a result of the study;

4.1 First Sub-Objective

Is there any meaningful difference between the experimental group and control group in terms of 'comprehension' skill according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?

Table 2: Pre-Post Test Results of Control Group for Textual Comprehension Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	24	3,00	0,884	46-4 .184 .000
Post test	24	3,95	0,690	

Table 3: Pre-Post Test Results of Experimental Group for Textual Comprehension Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	20	3,60	1,046	38-15 .359 .000
Post test	20	8,15	0,812	

In terms of reading comprehension skill, as a result of t test conducted on pretest and post test scores of both groups; it was identified that the arithmetic mean of control group was increased from 3,00 to 3,95 whereas it increased from 3,60 to 8,15 in experimental group. In both groups, it is seen that there is an increase in the positive way, but the increase in the experimental group is more significant than the control group. As a result, based on the results of achievement test in the experimental group in which the discourse analysis method was applied, we can conclude that their achievements have been increased on a large scale.

4.2 Second Sub-Objective

Is there any meaningful difference between the experimental group and control group in terms of 'analysis' skill according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?

Table 4: Pre-Post Test Results of Control Group for Textual Analysis Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	24	2,25	0,442	46-4 .836 .000
Post test	24	3,16	0,816	

Table 5: Pre-Post Test Results of Experimental Group for Textual Analysis Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	20	2,95	0,887	38-15 .131 .000
Post test	20	7,05	0,825	

In terms of textual analysis skill, as a result of t test conducted on pretest and post test scores of treatment and control groups; it was observed that arithmetic mean of control group was increased from 2,25 to 3,16 whereas it increased from 2,95 to 7,05 in experimental group. In both groups, it is seen that there is an increase in achievement level, but the increase in the experimental group is more significant than the control group. As a result, based on the results of achievement test, it was identified that the

achievement level of experimental group in textual analysis have been changed positively and on large scale.

4.3 Third Sub-Objective

Is there any meaningful difference between experimental group and control group in terms of 'making discourse' skill according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?

Table 6: Pre-Post Test Results of Control Group for Making Discourse Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	24	2,37	0,494	46-6 .879 .000
Post test	24	3,87	0,946	

Table 7: Pre-Post Test Results of Treatment Group for Making Discourse Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	20	2,75	0,910	38-16 .290 .000
Post test	20	7,35	0,875	

In terms of skill of making discourse, as a result of t test on pretest and post test scores of experimental and control groups; it was observed that arithmetic mean of control group was increased from 2,37 to 3,87 whereas it increased from 2,75 to 7,35 in experimental group. In both groups, it is seen that there is an increase in the positive way, but the increase in experimental group is more significant than the control group. As a result, according to the results of achievement test in the experiment group in which the discourse analysis method was applied, the achievements of the students have been changed significantly.

4.4 Fourth Sub-Objective

Is there any meaningful difference between experimental group and control group in terms of 'language use' skill on expressing thoughts during the process of textual analysis according to the evaluations made before and after the experiment?

Table 8: Pre-Post Test Results of Control Group for Use of Language Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	24	3,08	0,829	46-6 .880 .000
Post test	24	4,70	0,806	

Table 9: Pre-Post Test Results of Treatment Group for Use of Language Skill

	N	$\bar{X}$	S.S	Sd t p
Pre test	20	3,85	1,348	38-10 .201 .000
Post test	20	7,60	0,940	

In terms of language use skill, as a result of t test on pretest and post test scores of experimental and control groups; arithmetic mean of control group was increased from 3,08 to 4,70 whereas it increased from 3,85 to 7,60 in experimental group. In both

groups, it is seen that there is an increase in the positive way, but the increase in experimental group is more significant than the control group. As a result, according to the results of achievement test in the skill of use of language, students in experimental group improved largely.

4.5 Fifth Sub-Objective

What are the video-recorded thoughts and opinions of participants on discourse analysis method?

The opinions and thoughts of the students of experimental group on the use of discourse analysis method in lessons and its effect on the skills of comprehension, analysis, organization of thoughts and ideas which were acquired at the end of the analysis process and their views on their achievements in skillful and effective use of language, were gathered through semi-structured questions and recorded. Then, all of the responds of students in experimental group transcribed and analyzed through content analysis method. Therefore, as can be seen in the table below.

Through applying discourse analysis method in language and literature lessons, it can be concluded that their first acquisition and achievement was of cognitive area. In this study, through the data collected by the responds of students, areas such as thinking skills, meaningful learning, effective organization of ideas and native language awareness are categorized in the field of cognitive skills.

After discourse analysis method was applied, students stated their thoughts as; “my analysis and synthesis skills have had improved, I can make inferences, I can think critically, I can deepen my thoughts, I reach at reasonable inferences, I have developed independent thinking skills, the method encouraged me to think, it helped me to develop the skill of making sense by easing my process of thinking”. Therefore; it can be concluded that, discourse analysis method has important benefits for students in terms of thinking skills and they acknowledge these gains.

After applying discourse analysis method, students described language and literature lessons by using positive statements as entertaining, relaxing and encouraging self-confidence; and because they were actually producing ideas, making inferences so they owned and adopted these ideas and lessons and identified these with themselves. Increase, initiated by the method, in their involvement with the lessons, their interest and participation in the lessons, motivation, curiosity and the belief that they can be successful are very effective and important factors in achieving the objectives of the course as making meaningful and permanent learning possible rather than providing students with direct access to knowledge.

Table 10: Content Analysis of Opinions of Experimental Group

Theme	Category	Code		
Cognitive Skills	Thinking Skills	➤ Supporting expression by using language		
		➤ Analysis and synthesis skills		
		➤ Reaching the main theme		
		➤ Inference		
		➤ Interpretation		
		➤ Critical thinking		
		➤ Supporting thinking skills		
		➤ Induction		
		➤ Deepening of thoughts		
		➤ Independent thinking skills		
		➤ Facilitating thinking		
		➤ Encourage thinking		
Cognitive Skills	Meaningful Learning	➤ Entertaining		
		➤ Intriguing		
		➤ Relaxing		
		➤ Helping students to gain self-confidence		
		➤ Increasing the enthusiasm for participation in lesson		
		➤ Meaningful learning		
		➤ Increasing the success		
		➤ Interesting		
		➤ Making knowledge meaningful		
		➤ Motivating		
		Cognitive Skills	Effective organization of ideas	➤ Analyzing thoughts
				➤ Synthesizing thoughts
➤ Holistic thinking				
➤ Organizing thoughts				
➤ Expressing ideas in an effective and organized way				
Cognitive Skills	Native Language Awareness	➤ Revealing language aptitudes		
		➤ Increasing language awareness		
		➤ Recognizing the flexible structure of the language		
		➤ Fluency		
		➤ Language awareness		
Affective Skills	Social Skills	➤ Socializing		
		➤ Communication skills		
		➤ Making students feel that individual thought is valuable		
		➤ Making daily-life easy		
		➤ Understanding and interpretation of people's behaviors		

After students learnt to use discourse analysis method to analyze and reach at the meaning of texts in the language and literature lessons, it was possible for them to analyze and synthesize their thoughts, to express them effectively and properly, to present them with proper organizational skills and to get a holistic view and idea. This shows that students gained important outcomes in terms of skills of making discourse which is one the sub-objectives of this study. Students' statements about their outcomes on this area, supports the findings of achievement test, and it stresses on a fundamental and important outcome about the language and literature courses and its objectives.

The last cognitive skill, derived through content analysis of opinion forms was mother language awareness. Students stated that after using discourse analysis method in language and literature lessons, they were able to reveal their language abilities more easily, their awareness and consciousness about language, language choices and language in use were increased, they were able to more recognize flexible structure of language, they got fluency in language and their use of language was more of a conscious mental process, and they expressed that their lessons were clearer and meaningful for them. They reached at a consensus on the opinion that they got a level of consciousness about use of language while their awareness about language increased in both in language and literature lessons and in their daily life.

The second outcome for students gained by using discourse analysis method in language and literature lessons was in affective field. When we look at the outcomes of students in affective area; socialization, communication skills, getting the feeling that individual thought is valuable and appreciated, self-esteem, and facilitating everyday life and so on can be categorized in this field.

5. Conclusion

Compared to regular and traditional instructional methods, integrating discourse analysis method into language and literature lessons created big success on students in terms of not only comprehension and use of language skills but also made a great contribution to their thinking and communication skills. Additionally, integration of discourse analysis method to language and literature lessons makes these lessons more interesting and attractive, and so it creates more opportunities for students to attend and actively participate in these lessons. Moreover, use of this method in language and literature lessons equips students with skills and outcomes to be able to participate lessons actively, so it is thought that integration of this method into language and literature lessons would bring a multidirectional success.

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